

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER PROBLEMS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The online shopping involves buying and selling of goods and services through online. Online shopping means buying and selling of the goods and services online; internet is the best source to use this tool. The main objective of the study is to study the consumer's expectation towards online shopping and to study about the customer's opinion towards the problems in online shopping. For this purpose a sample of 270 was collected from the respondents were percentage analysis, ranking on Kendall's correlation and chi square was used as tools to analyse the data and the conclusion is that based on the customers perception towards service provided by the companies Flipkart has the highest priority to the service provided and the priority can be given by the customers to purchase their products in this website.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Problems & Perception.

Introduction:

Online shopping is defined as the process a customer takes to purchase a service or product over the internet. In other words, a consumer may at his or her leisure buy from the comfort of their own home products from an online store. This concept was first demonstrated before the World Wide Web (WWW) was in use with real time transaction processed from a domestic television. The technology used was called Videotext and was first demonstrated in 1979 by M. Aldrick who designed and installed systems in the United Kingdom. India had an internet user base of about 354 million as of June 2015 and is expected to cross 500 million in 2016. Despite being the second-largest user base in world, only behind China (650 million, 48% of population), the penetration of e-commerce is low compared to markets like the United States (266 million, 84%), or France (54 M, 81%), but is growing at an unprecedented rate, adding around 6 million new entrants every month. The industry consensus is that growth is at an inflection point. In India, cash on delivery is the most preferred payment method, accumulating 75% of the e-retail activities. Demand for international consumer products (including long-tail items) is growing much faster than in-country supply from authorised distributors and e-commerce offerings.

Review of Literature:

Hermes (2000) in this study concluded that the consumers not only look for products, but also for online services. Some companies have online customer services available 24 hours. Therefore, even after business hours, customers can ask questions; get necessary support or assistance, which has provided convenience to consumers

Hofacker and Wang et al., (2005) in their study shows that convenient of the internet is one of the impacts on consumers' willingness to buy online (Wang et al., 2005). Online shopping is available for customers around the clock comparing to traditional store as it is open 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

The Tech Faq, (2008) in this study shows that 58 percent chose to shop online because they could shop after-hours, when the traditional stores are closed and 61 percent of the respondents selected to shop online because they want to avoid crowds and wailing lines, especially in holiday shopping

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the reasons for the problems towards online shopping
- ✓ To know the association between experience of online shopping and demographic variables

Scope of the Study:

The study is to know about customers delay or hesitate to make decision for shopping online and to determine the reasons and suggestions for the problems faced by the customers. India has witnessed a major breakthrough E-commerce success stories particularly in e-retail in Consumer Electronics & Fashion Apparel & Home Furnishing segments. E-commerce creates new opportunities for entrepreneurial start-ups. Ease of Internet access, Safe and secure payment modes coupled with aggressive marketing by E-Commerce Giants has revolutionized this segment. Rapid development in mobile technology has given way to Mobile Commerce with many E-Commerce companies shifting to App only model. The main scope of the study is that it will be helpful for the companies to maintain their quality of service based on customers in future period of time.

Research Methodology:

The study is intended to analyse the customers’ problem during online purchase. The methodology of the study includes

Research Design: Research design is the detailed plan of conducting a research study. Descriptive research design has been used in the study.

Descriptive Research Design: Descriptive analysis attempts to explain systematically a trend, and provides data concerning attitudes and preferences towards a problem.

Sample Area: The data has been collected from Coimbatore District as it has a high residential density with people from all over Tamilnadu due to the high migration influx in recent years. The population is quite heterogeneous, with various dimensions such as religion, caste, customs, traditions, social hierarchy, language, literacy, education, occupation, income etc.

Sample Technique: Sampling technique is the choice of a subset of people from among a huge population to estimate characteristics of the 270 respondents. The simple random technique has been chosen for this study.

Instrument Design: Personal interview method

Structure of the Instrument: for collecting primary data, structured questionnaire has been used.

Tools and Techniques Used for Analysis: Simple percentage analysis, chi-square test, and weighted average method

Limitations of the Study:

The study has got certain limitation of which a few are listed below:

- ✓ The results and findings are confined to a limited area.
- ✓ The opinions of the respondents may be biased.
- ✓ Time and resource constraint.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Particulars	Factors	No of Respondents	%
	Male	190	70.4
	Female	80	29.6
	Total	270	100
Marital status	Married	55	20.4
	Unmarried	215	79.6
	Total	270	100
Area of residing	Rural	217	80.4
	Urban	53	19.6
	Total	270	100
Age	Up to 20 years	65	24.1
	20-40 years	95	35.2
	40-60 years	84	31.1
	Above 60 years	26	9.6
	Total	270	100

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that out of 270 respondents, 70.4% are male and 29.6% are female. It can be concluded that male respondents prefer to shop online than female. 20.4% were married and 79.6% were unmarried. 80.4% of the respondents were from rural area and the rest 19.6% of the respondents from urban area. 35.2% of the respondents aged between 20-40 years, 31.1% of the respondents aged between 40-60 years, 24.1% of the respondents aged up to 20 years and the remaining 9.6% of the respondents aged above 60 years

Ranking Based on Kendall’s Correlation:

Factors		Wide range of products	Free door delivery	Low cost	Discounts and offers	Quality of products	24*7 shopping facility
Wide range of products	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.165**	-.187**	-.227**	-.131*	-.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.002	.000	.000	.010	.140
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Free door delivery	Correlation Coefficient	-.165**	1.000	-.107*	-.202**	-.202**	-.071
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.	.038	.000	.000	.200
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Low cost	Correlation Coefficient	-.187**	-.107*	1.000	-.214**	-.119*	-.204**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.038	.	.000	.017	.000
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270

Discounts and offers	Correlation Coefficient	-.227**	-.202**	-.214**	1.000	-.145**	-.055
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.004	.301
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Quality of products	Correlation Coefficient	-.131*	-.202**	-.119*	-.145**	1.000	-.210**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	.000	.017	.004	.	.000
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
24*7 shopping facility	Correlation Coefficient	-.079	-.071	-.204**	-.055	-.210**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.140	.200	.000	.301	.000	.
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).							

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that the Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance used for the study was based on Kendall's correlation factors are negative and with that factor are not correlated with each other.

Descriptive Statistics for Level of Awareness towards Online Shopping Sites:

Shopping Sites	N	Mean Score	Std. Deviation
Flipkart	270	2.28	.832
Amazon	270	1.49	.557
Snap deal	270	1.51	.620
Jabong	270	1.50	.789
Myntra	270	1.91	.748
Local banya	270	2.36	.641
Homeshop18	270	2.56	.653
Infibeam	270	2.51	.655
Shopclues	270	2.34	.617
Firstery	270	2.44	.738
eBay	270	2.05	.666
Paytm	270	2.27	.648
Valid N (listwise)	270		

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that the descriptive statistics on level of awareness towards various websites were the above mid mean value (2.0) shows that the sites have high awareness and the websites which has highest awareness in the market is Flipkart as the mean value is greater than other websites at 2.28 as per analysis.

Demographic Variables and Experience of Online Shopping:

Demographic Variables	Chi-Square	P Values	Significant/ Not Significant
Gender	39.002	0.000	S
Age	1.364	0.000	S
Marital status	9.997	0.019	S
Place	33.357	0.000	S
Educational qualification	1.004	0.000	S
Occupation	16.487	0.170	NS
Monthly income	1.162	0.000	S

S- Significant (P value = 0.05)

Interpretation:

The above table shows that there is a significant association between experience of online shopping and demographic variables like gender, age, marital status, place, educational qualification, and monthly income are less than 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. There is no significant association between experience of online shopping and demographic variables of occupation as the value is greater than 0.05.

Findings:

Percentage Analysis:

- ✓ Male respondents prefer to shop online than female.

- ✓ Unmarried respondents prefer to shop online than married.
- ✓ Rural area respondents prefer to shop online than urban.

Most of the respondents prefer to shop online were under the age group of 20-40 years

Chi Square:

- ✓ There is a significant association between experience of online shopping, frequency of online shopping, occasion of purchase through online websites, average amount spent for online shopping and demographic variables like gender, age, marital status, place, educational qualification, and monthly income.

Mean Rank:

- ✓ The website which has highest awareness in the market is Flipkart as the mean value is greater than other websites at 2.28 as per analysis.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The companies related to online shopping can promote their brand and products related with them more with male persons who are unmarried as they are using they are using the websites more when compared to other persons based on the study.
- ✓ More advertisements can be given through social media as most of the persons who are working in private organisations use the company's website to purchase a lot.
- ✓ The frequency of shopping online by the customers was made during heavy discount period and the companies can try to increase the frequency of providing more discounts so that the volume of trade can be increased and it leads to increase in customer base for the companies.
- ✓ The company concentrate more on free door delivery for the clients who shop online as the customers prefer that and if the same is done for rural areas then the volume can be increased in future period of time.

Conclusion:

Today the amount of trade that is conducted electronically using online shopping has increased with a wide spread usage of internet and technology. Online shopping includes transferring of funds online, marketing over internet, buying and selling of goods and services etc. The online shopping has become more popular among the customers. For online shopping the customers should have knowledge about usage of internet and computer. Internet has become the centre of not only our personal and social lives, but also our business and professional lives. The main objective of the study is to know why customers delay or hesitate to make decision for shopping online and to determine the reasons and suggestions for the problems faced by the customers and the conclusion is that based on the customers perception towards service provided by the companies Flipkart has the highest priority to the service provided and the priority can be given by the customers to purchase their products in this website.

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